

Table A1: SO and GH user features of the data collected.

Feature Name	Data Type	Description
Stack Overflow features		
badge_counts_bronze	Integer	Count of bronze badges earned by the user on SO
badge_counts_silver	Integer	Count of silver badges earned by the user on SO
badge_counts_gold	Integer	Count of gold badges earned by the user on SO
reputation	Integer	User's total reputation score on SO
reputation_change_year	Integer	Change in reputation over the past year
reputation_change_month	Integer	Change in reputation over the past month
reputation_change_week	Integer	Change in reputation over the past week
reputation_change_day	Integer	Change in reputation over the past day
reputation_change_quarter	Integer	Change in reputation over the past quarter
creation_date	DateTime	Date the user account was created
user_type	String	Type of user (e.g., registered, moderator)
accept_rate	Float	Rate of accepted answers for the user on SO
location	String	User's self-reported location
website_url	String	User's personal or professional website
link	String	Link to the user profile
collectives	String	SO collectives the user is part of
timed_penalty_date	DateTime	Date of last timed penalty
account_id	Integer	Unique identifier for the user's Stack Exchange account
user_id	Integer	Unique identifier for the user on SO
is_employee	Boolean	Whether the user is an employee on SO
display_name	String	User's display name on SO
last_access_date	DateTime	Date of the user's last access on SO
last_modified_date	DateTime	Date of the user's last modification on SO
GitHub features		
login	String	User's GH login name
bio	String	User's bio on GH
company	String	Company user is affiliated with
email	String	User's public email on GH
name	String	User's entered name
createdAt	DateTime	Date the GH account was created
id	Integer	Unique ID of the GH user
location	String	User's self-reported location on GH
url	String	URL to the user's GH profile
organizations	String	Organizations the user is affiliated with on GH
followers	Integer	Number of followers on GH
following	Integer	Number of accounts the user follows on GH
repositories	Integer	Number of repositories owned by the user
stargazers	Integer	Number of stars received by the user
starredRepositories	Integer	Number of repositories starred by the user
repositoriesContributedTo	Integer	Number of repositories the user has contributed to
gists	Integer	Number of gists the user has created
issues	Integer	Number of issues engaged by the user
pullRequests	Integer	Number of pull requests made by the user